

Olduvai Gorge – Chronostratigraphie, Climate, Ecosystem & Hominin Evolution

Structured Chronostratigraphic Reference Tool

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2021

This document is a working chronostratigraphic synthesis compiled for personal research purposes, representing a revised and architecturally restructured version of an earlier compilation (Variant 1). It integrates data from primary literature across stratigraphy, geochronology, palaeoclimatology, palaeoecology, and palaeoanthropology, with all entries referenced to their source publications. It incorporates updated chronological data from the Olduvai Gorge Coring Project (OGCP), including dating by Deino et al. (2020/2021). It is not a peer-reviewed work and should be treated accordingly: entries reflect the state of the literature as consulted during compilation and may not incorporate more recent findings. Errors and gaps are possible. The author welcomes corrections.

My Notes and My Question Marks (n.a.; ?)

Marker Unit column cited from: [A.L. Deino, 2012, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.004], [L. J. McHenry & I.G. Stanistreet, 2018, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2017.12.006],

New dating OGCP (new [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109751] from [A.L. Deino et al., 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990]).

Frm.	Age	Milankovitch	Lake Parasequences	Lake Cycle	Marker Unit	New dating OGCP	Tuff Marker / Facies Archaeological levels & Hominin finds Palaeoclimate & Environment / Various authors
Naisiusiu Beds							
							Tephra component from Oldonyo Lengai is the boundary between Ndotu Beds - Naisiusiu Beds (Hay 1976) [D.R. Sherrod et al., 2013, DOI: 10.3133/ofr20131306].
Ndotu Beds Upper Ndotu Beds							Upper Ndotu Beds age range between 60 and 32 ka, based on the available evidence [W.B. Reiner et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1002/ajpa.23292].
							OH 83, early <i>Homo sapiens</i> (partial calvarium), near archeological locality PLK and geological locality 23 (Hay, 1976), situated on the downthrown side of FLK Fault between the Fourth and 5th Faults on the north side of the main gorge [Whitney Brooke Reiner, 2017, (Dissertation), https://escholarship.org/uc/item/83w0b1k1], geologically dated to ca. 60 – 32 ka. OH 83 are at the fairly small and gracile range of modern human cranial variation [W.B. Reiner et al., 2017, DOI: 10.1002/ajpa.23292], [I.-M. Maillou-Fernández et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.07.032].
							OH-1968 (skull fragment), partially <i>in situ</i> in Upper Ndotu levels (Von Zieten, 2009), but whose origin and study are uncertain [I.-M. Maillou-Fernández et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.07.032].
							OH 11 (palate and maxillary arch) <i>Homo sp.</i> found on the surface in western DK and assigned to the Ndotu Bed (Hay, 1976, pp. 159; Leakey 1971, pp. 230) [I.-M. Maillou-Fernández et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.07.032].
Lower Ndotu Beds							Lower Ndotu Beds The geological record at Victoria Cabrera Site (VCS), dating back to around 75–86 ka BP (corresponds to MIS 5a), is a Lower Ndotu fluvial terrace deposit (Uribelarrea et al., in this volume), just prior to Upper Ndotu sedimentation, which can be approximately dated 90 ka BP. Based upon chronology, we place VCS within 90–75 ka BP. The MSA lithic industry is characteristic for prepared core methods, especially discoid and Levallois, with some "domestic-type" retouched pieces (sidescrapers, denticulates and notches), scarce heavy-duty, and a total absence of points [I.-M. Maillou-Fernández et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.07.032]. The faunal assemblage at VCS includes Alcephaginae, Antilopinae, Equidae, Hippopotamidae, Ostrich (<i>Struthio camelus</i> , sensu Dauphin et al. 1996), Testudinidae and Rodentia [I.-M. Maillou-Fernández et al., 2019, DOI: 10.1016/j.quaint.2019.07.032].
Ndotu Beds basal contact						0.50 ± 0.04 Ma	
	700 ka						Norkilli Tuff (Hay 1976) [D.R. Sherrod et al., 2013, DOI: 10.3133/ofr20131306].
							Bed IV archaeological record at HEB [J.K. Njau et al., 2020, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109773].
							... Diamictite, Sandy siltstone, Gravel conglomerate,
Masek Bed base			(n.a., level do not exist by the author)			0.82 ± 0.08 Ma	(n.a., level do not exist by the author)
Bed IV			Parasq. 11 top				Sub-Masek unconformity,
			Parasq. 11 base				... clay(ey) ...
			Parasq. 10 top				Paraconformity, pedogenic features 1 m till the discontinuity with Masek Bed unexcavated. ---HEB top ---
			Lake shallowing up.				L1, claystone, sharp contact top, archaeologically sterile. Nearshore lake with drying out surfaces affected by pedogenesis and elsewhere ostracod-bearing. The claystone facies indicate a transgression of Palaeolake Olduvai across the HEB site.
			Lake deepening up. Parasq. 10 base				L2, L2a, clayey sandstone, sharp contact with L1 and diffuse contact with L2b; archaeologically moderate (between 40 and 100 fossil and artifact specimens), sandy braided fluvial and overbank deposits. Lacustrine flooding surface. L2b, silty sandstone, archaeologically rare (less than 40 fossil and artifact specimens), sandy braided fluvial channel.
							Paraconformity, intraclasts Thin claystone. Between level L2b and L3, we uncovered a nearly complete postcranial skeleton of an Elephantid (rest on claystone above siltstone atop Level 3). Overlies the archaeological Level 1 of Leakey (hier, L3), and is associated with artifacts, indicating a possible butchery site. Numerous handaxes made from basalt, quartzite, and phonolite.
			Parasq. 9 top Parasq. 9 base				L3, sandy siltstone overlain by a thin claystone, archaeologically dense (over 100 fossil and artifact specimens). Nearshore lake with occasional drying out surfaces (shallowing upward). Higher L3. Lower L3. Abandoned fluvial channel (low energy) filled by occasional flood events

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	1.8683 Ma				F1, duration ~2.57 kyr	1.8667–1.8643 Ma					
	1.8856 Ma				D2, dry	1.8856 Ma					
	1.900 ± 0.015 Ma				W1, duration ~7.6 kyr D1, driest	(1.900 ± 0.015 Ma; Deino et al., 2020) 1.956 ± 0.031 Ma [H. Stollhofen et al., 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102910, Manuscript]	Bed I basalt at 90 m. - The basalt lava effusion at 1.956 ± 0.031 Ma [Ar/Ar date OGCP Core2A: Deino et al., in press], within error of ~1.94 Ma (astronomically derived date: Stanistreet et al., 2020a).	Bed I Basalt, 1.877 ± 0.013 Ma (Deino, 2012) Mafic Tuff III (east) Mafic Tuff II (west) Bed I lavas (east) [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.sedgeo.2016.03.026].			
Lower Bed I											
							In situ ~2.0 Ma trees (Loc. 66e) [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.09.011].		Olduvai's oldest Oldowan [H. Stollhofen et al., 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102910, Manuscript].		
							Lacustrine suspension fallout.		(n.a., level do not exist by the author)		
							Tuff IA, (1.88 ± 0.05 Ma, Deino, 2012). Tuff IA (1.88 +/- 0.05 Ma) [J. Mercader et al., 2020, DOI: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-49789/v1, Pre-print].		Tuff IA, ~1.98 Ma (1.976 ± 0.004 Ma, Walter et al., 1992) - Facies characteristics of the volcanic sandstones of the rhyolitic Tuff IA unit classify them as shallow braided fluvial deposits. -----Top Loc. 68, T 168 -----	Tuff IA (1.88 +/- 0.05 Ma) (?) - Grassland encroachment on woodlands. (?) - Grassland encroachment on woodlands occurred twice during the deposition of Tuff IA. (?)	
			Lake-parasequence boundarie				Major erosional unconformity.		Paraconformitie Erosional surface preceding Tuff A. Disconformitie 9 (hiatal surface)		
			- One of the two succeeding precessional cycles, each of about 19.5 ka duration [H. Stollhofen et al., 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.20.102910, Manuscript].				Lake retreat and incision of drainages due to base level lowering. Claystone. - Lacustrine suspension fallout. - Establishment and successive Bed I expansions of Paleolake Olduvai finally centred on the area between Sixth and FLK Faults (Hay, 1976; Hay and Kyser, 2001; Stollhofen and Stanistreet, 2012) to deposit a thick succession mainly of lacustrine olive waxy clays (Hay, 1976).		Fluvio-lacustrine deltaic unit with the last two subdivisions least affected by syndepositional faulting effects. - Major transgression of Paleolake Olduvai. Depositional Unit IV. - Lake level fall and the dried-out land surface became most likely flushed by meteoric waters to favor burrowing and rooting. Subsequently, the lithics and faunal assemblage accumulated on top of this surface. Diamictitic flow unit (?) Diamictitic flow unit (?) Diamictitic flow unit (?)	A sixth Oldowan cluster was positioned 3 m beneath Tuff IA (>1.88 ± 0.05 Ma) (T2). Fauna comprises bovids, suids, equids, and large mammals, with Plio-Pleistocene cercopithecines from grassy niches (cf. Theropithecus oswaldi) and perennial water indicators (Chelonia, Crocodylus, and Hippopotamus). Woody dicots and grasses booming and busting cyclically.	
			Lake-parasequence boundarie						Paraconformitie (lake-parasequence boundarie) Disconformitie 8 (hiatal surface)		
									Depositional Unit III. Deepening upward fan-delta toe. (n.a., => 2.0225 Ma) - The sandy waxy claystone covers the bone and tool assemblage (100; high proportion of flaking debitage). Waxy claystone Sandy waxy olive-green claystone with insect burrows and/or roots. Records a transgression of the shallow lake environment. Disconformitie 7 (hiatal surface) Claystone Diamictite (?) Sandy waxy claystone		
			Lake-parasequence boundarie						Paraconformitie (lake-parasequence boundarie)		
			- The two major lacustrine dominated intervals indicate wetter periods, when the lake flooded its margins, interpreted as the expression of two succeeding precessional cycles, each of about 19.5 ka duration [H. Stollhofen et al., 2021, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.20.102910, Manuscript].						Depositional Unit II. Dominantly lacustrine fan-delta toe. - Major transgression of the Paleolake. - A change in phytolith morphological presence coincides with the formation of the assemblage and the subsequent westward lake flooding. Fine to coarse sandstone (?) Disconformitie 6 (hiatal surface) Pebbly clay diamictite – mudflow (?) with insect burrows and/or roots Sandy diamictite (?) Diamictite (?) Claystone Diamictite (?) Sandy waxy claystone Diamictite (?) Erosional base of the claystone Diamictite (?) Medium (clayey) sandstone Disconformitie 5 (hiatal surface) (n.a., lake-parasq. boundarie ?). Sandy diamictite (?) Fine to coarse sandstone (?)		
			Lake-parasequence boundarie						Paraconformitie (lake-parasequence boundarie)		
									Depositional Unit I. Subaerial debris flow dominated fan. - A change from grass-dominated landscape and sedges for Level 4, to a woodier landscape (some trees and shrubs and/or mixed woodland) for subsequent levels, and the disappearance of sedges. - These alternations between domination of C3 and C4 grasses might relate to changes between more humid and drier conditions. Level 0 Braided fluvial Deeply mudcracked and burrowed hiatal surface. Disconformitie 5 Level 1 (n.a., => 2.0176 Ma) - A subsequent lake level fall and associated incision then rather effectively removed most of the Level 2 sandstone. - The few artifacts in the Level 1 low-viscosity debris flow above are interpreted to have eroded from both underlying Levels 2 and 3 and were entrained into Level 1. Sandy diamictites (massflows) with termite burrowed and deeply mudcracked. - Dominated by characteristic grass phytoliths (Bulliform flabellate, Acute bulbosus, GSSCP, and Elongate dentate, and low abundance of palm characteristic Spheroid echinate. - The abundance of termitaria, burrowing down particularly from hiatal surfaces, would accord with the envisioned savannah vegetation pattern. Incision Disconformitie 4 Level 2 - Fluvial sandstone with both units hosting the majority of the Tr 168 assemblage. The base of the Level 2 sandstone also erodes into the underlying claystone to displace artifacts and bone. A subsequent lake level fall and associated Massive pebble to boulder conglomerates. Medium to coarse sandstones bearing lithic and clay granules, as well as scattered pebbles represent the third facies type. - Phytolith assemblage mainly composed of grass characteristic phytoliths and Elongate entire; Saddle and Bilobate types from C4 plants. Higher amounts of		

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										incision. - Level 2 yielded 88 total lithic artifacts.	characteristic dicotyledonous wood/bark phytoliths (>20%) were noted in the upper samples.			
										Level 3 - Subsequent lake level rise. Low energy lake-shore. - In terms of Paleolake Olduvai lake level, hominin evidence occurs exactly at the transition from a lake lowstand to a lake level rise. - Level 3 yielded 100 lithic artifacts.	Olive-green laminated sandy waxy claystone unit (<4–20 mm thick); implies deposition in a shallow lake environment, affected by aeolian input of disseminated sand grains (Albert et al., 2015; Stanistreet et al., 2018a, 2020b). - Grasses dominate. Dicotyledonous wood/bark and leaves were present.			
										Pre-Level 3	3 rd diamicton unit - Tree horizon of Habermann et al. (2016) at Loc. 66e.	Pre-(artificial) Level 3 erosional surface Sandy diamicton (?) with insect burrows and/or roots. - The tree find about 2 km further to the east at Locs 68 and 69 [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2015.09.011].		
										Level 4 - Level 4 diamicton has a pronounced up to 1.2 m topography. - Records a succession of three diamictonic flow units, each separated by hiatal surfaces. Lake level fall and the dried-out land surface became most likely flushed by meteoric waters to favor burrowing and rooting. Subsequently, the lithics and faunal assemblage accumulated on top of this surface. - Hominins most probably utilized the lake margins at times of lower lake levels, when these were subaerially exposed (top surface of Level 4), but increased flushing by fresh waters and development of grasslands and river-fed freshwater wetlands in the course of the onset of a wet phase.	Medium to coarse sandstones Disconformity 3 2 nd diamicton unit (sandy diamicton) with insect burrows and/or roots (hiatal surface) (?) 1 st diamicton unit Sandy diamicton (?) with insect burrows and/or roots.			
										Level 5	Pebble to boulder conglomerate.			
										Disconformity 2 (hiatal surface) (n.a., lake-parasequence boundary ?)				
										Level 6	Diamictite with insect burrows and/or roots, and with mudcrack fill from pebble to boulder conglomerate stratum		At the contact between the Ngorongoro Formation and Bed I, near a low sinuosity meandering channel flowing east, three additional Oldowan assemblages preserved 4.6 m below Tuff IA in TS, in an environmental context of open woodlands (a mixture of C ₃ and C ₄ plants, animals were drinking from a similar water source).	
Ngorongoro Volcanic Fm. (NVF)						2,003 ± 0.006 Ma	CFCT (Tuff Marker NgP)		We interpret this unit as resulting from a lateral flow transformation of the 'primary' CFCT pyroclastic flow unit.					
									Disconformity 1 (hiatal surface) ----- Base T 168 -----					
							Mafic Tuff I,						Laharic inundation buried synchronous woodland landscapes and Oldowan industries nearby. Floodplain palaeosols in trench no.5 (TS). ----- End Ewass Oldupa site, Loc. 63 -----	
						2,030 ± 0.0013 Ma	Naabi Ignimbrite, catastrophic volcanic eruption and associated debris flow [J. Mercader et al., 2021, DOI: 10.1038/s41467-020-20176-2].							
						2,047 ± 0.003 Ma	Orkeri Ignimbrite (Tuff Marker NgN), brown-beige, lithic- and pumice-rich ash-lapilli tuff at the First Fault [J.M. Habermann et al., 2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.jhevol.2016.03.026]. Orkeri Tuff in the age modeling 2.0471 ± 0.003 Ma [A.L. Deino et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990].							
						2,080 ± 0.0041 Ma	Tuff Marker NgG, (tuff from 147.8–152.7 mbs in Core 2A: 2A-150 [Deino et al., 2020]) (new OGCP Core 2A/3A [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109751]).							
							Between Tuff Marker NgF and NgG, conglomerates/diamictites (new OGCP Core 2A/3A [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109751]). At ? mbs 2.077 ± 0.002 Ma (Ar/Ar age) (new OGCP Core 2A/3A [A. Rodriguez-Cintas et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109928, Journal Pre-proof] from [A.L. Deino et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109990]).							
							Tuff Marker NgF (new OGCP Core 2A/3A [I.G. Stanistreet et al., 2020, DOI: 10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109751]).							